

PROSPECT OF BORDERLESS CURRICULUM IN THE POST-HUMAN ERA: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES IN RELATION TO THE NIGERIAN INITIAL TEACHER PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the opportunities and challenges of borderless curriculum in the post-human era as the alternative to reimagine a better future premised on initial teacher education. The paper comes against the background that curriculum projects remain nationalized, depriving learners and educators of opportunities to learn from the best educational practices from other parts of the world. The paper is located in post-humanism, where borderless curriculum through the aid of technology can be positioned to respond positively to human tragedies such as war, systematic racism, human trafficking and conflict. Borderless curriculum involves shifting from the initial traditional pedagogical practices in order to learn by harvesting best practices across borders to reimagine a comprehensive initial teacher education that addresses the lived realities of the learners globally. The paper argues that the post-human era provides a platform for nations to share knowledge in the virtual and blended space to deconstruct prejudices while evoking living and working together across through borderless curriculum and spaces to improve initial teacher education globally.

KEYWORDS: Borderless Curriculum, Teacher Education, post-human Era, Global Challenges, Pedagogical Practices

Introduction

The need for a borderless curriculum was borne out of an observation that there had been a wide knowledge gap in the curriculum practiced outside the borders that deprived learners and lecturers of opportunities to enrich themselves with global education trends. It was clear that the initial teacher education was designed to primarily serve the interest of citizens or people living in a particular state, with little or no emphasis on how initial teachers can be instrumental in contexts outside their state borders, let alone national borders. Moreso, it was clear that while universities are expecting to explore knowledge production and dissemination far and wide, it was not happening at a rate which could fully equip initial teachers for the global stage, denoting a minimalistic approach to initial teacher education. This is despite the pressure from the industry and corporate world on the faculty and administration of universities to internationalize their campuses, curricula and classrooms (Atalar, 2020) to meet the new demands placed by post-humanism. Despite the pressure, some countries still train initial teachers for the national context. For example, in the US, student teachers are basically trained to teach in US states' context only and similarly, in Nigeria and South Africa (SA), the approach to initial teacher education is rather exclusively to the countries' contexts. However, in a global context, where migration has become the order of the day, the development of initial teachers should move beyond the borders, local context and methodologies and embrace a pluviosity approach to teacher education so that the teachers can at least teach competitively across the globe (Kilinc et al., 2018; Moyo et al., 2022; Omodan, 2022). Post-humanism has made this possible through various technological devices and programmes. Consequently, citizens connect directly with others, regardless of geography, in social networking, commerce, politics, and science (Bethlehem, 2014; Dube et al., 2022).

It is in this context that the study tries to investigate the prospects and challenges of borderless curriculum in initial teacher development in Nigeria. The researcher is optimistic that a new curriculum approach to initial teacher development is positioned to ignite modes of working together that can also develop solutions to international problems (Al-Youbi & Zahed, 2020) by having a comprehensive approach to issues available to learners across a range of contexts. To achieve this, he is of the view that shifting our attention to a borderless curriculum can give an impetus to train and develop initial teachers to work across borders in different contexts and with different learners. The borderless curriculum within the auspices of a post-human era is the very idea that argues that people can step outside their boundaries, potentially embracing every form of life and every technological structure (Valera, 2014).

It is an approach of knowledge sharing, exchange programmes for students and staff and promoting dual degrees, which enable initial teachers to comprehensively understand both the possibilities and ambivalences associated with teaching and learning within and outside of political borders.

It is quite commendable that various kinds of researches have been conducted on borderless curriculum in various fields by different countries and universities as part of the internationalization of education. For example, a researches on borderless curriculum had been conducted in countries such as the US or Germany. The idea of those researches was intended to better understand how to take advantage of the potential of cross-border content for educational goals in the European Union's policy context (Pepler et al., 2016).

Another international project conducted by Crosling, Edwards and Schroder (2008), sought to prepare graduates for employment in 'the global economy' where they may work

internationally. Many universities have adopted a strategy of ‘internationalizing the curriculum. While the idea seemed noble, they highlighted that staff resistance occurred in that participation in the programme, which was seen as contravening traditional notions of academic autonomy.

Another noticeable international collaboration was Norway with countries such as Uganda, Kenya, Mozambique, Malawi, Zambia, Tanzania, and Sudan. The collaboration sought advantageous positions in trade, commerce, and business (Breidlid, 2013).

Cognizant of the foregoing research, it is obvious that this paper is unique and contributes knowledge in the internationalization of initial teacher education in the following ways: firstly, it focuses on borderless curriculum in Nigeria with reference to initial teacher education. Secondly, it is unique in the sense that it uses post-human thinking, where the use of technology can bridge knowledge, cultural and social divide between the two countries in the initial teacher education programme.

Such an approach is believed to be inevitable given that today’s classrooms have become cosmopolitan centres, “comprised of a mixture of different people from differing geographical, cultural, and linguistic backgrounds, with significant historical trajectories of movement” (Hawkins, 2014).

The paper suggests that embracing post-human thinking could propel Nigeria as a nation towards recognizing the need for a borderless curriculum using various technological systems available to narrow the knowledge gap of (and about) the other. This could mitigate against threats and associated prejudice related to what does (and does not) happen on one side of the border or the other, thus enhancing initial teacher education’s capacity to address the lived realities of learners across contexts, as new ways of teaching and learning are ignited through post-human framework.

Theoretical Framework: Post-Human Theory

The paper is hinged on post-human theory. Seltin (2009) argued that post-human does not signify the end of man; rather it signifies the end of certain misguided ways of conceiving human identity and the nature of human relations to the social and natural environments, other species, and technology. Post-human research is neofoundationalist in that it aims at re-grounding concepts and practices of subjectivity in a world fraught with contradictory socio-economic developments and major internal fractures (Braidotti, 2016). Therefore, post-humanist thought moves the centre of contemporary philosophical reflections from the question of technological possibilities and of its alleged ethical limits to the question of the limits of man, interwoven in his original essence (Valera, 2014). This theory is seen as a relevant frame within which to couch an argument for borderless curriculum that is premised on understanding the impossibility of offering actual exchange opportunities to all initial teacher education students from Nigeria and beyond.

Technological advances premised on post-human thinking allow reimagining new teaching methods in preparing initial teachers for global engagement. The issue of technology is central to the post-anthropocentric predicament (Braidotti, 2103) and should be exploited to build new meaning and possibilities for initial teacher education for Nigeria. As argued by Braidotti (2016), the high degrees of technological mediation and the undoing of the nature-culture divide create a series of paradoxes, such as an electronically linked pan-humanity that is split by convulsive internal fractures (Braidotti, 2016). In premising a borderless curriculum within posthumanism, the goal is not so much a hyper-technological appliance of

the human being but a progressive elimination and fluidization of the differences (Valera, 2014, p. 483). The post-human theory in the context of this paper is a move towards a wall-less or building-less classroom where students in Nigeria can be taught the same content and engage the same assignments, and each other, regardless of distance and time. This way of reframing initial teacher education could better prepare teachers for a cosmopolitan environment; a borderless curriculum seeks to ignite these conversations at a small scale with the hope that ideas from it will develop and influence policy making in Nigeria and other countries that will join the practice as it develops.

Opportunities Associated With Borderless Curriculum in the Post-human Era

Some of the opportunities associated with borderless curriculum practice in relation to initial teacher education in Nigeria are discussed as follows:

Broadening initial teacher education capacity: Judging from the pedagogical experience and observation of the researcher in Nigeria, with students having comprehensive understanding of the Nigerian system of education in terms of assessment, grading, standardized testing, and policies relating to education, there is need for a more comprehensive approach to teacher education that foregrounds educational and curriculum issues outside the borders. Cognizant of this, there is need to broaden initial education to include elements of comparative education where students cover other components outside their context and a borderless curriculum positions itself as an approach to bridge the knowledge gap.

The borderless curriculum approach could allow students to appreciate their strengths and weaknesses as they prepare to engage in the teaching field and, more so, help curriculum planners for initial teacher education to rethink a comparative approach to education rather than exclusively focusing on specific and individual provinces, states, or countries. Thus, it is believed that a borderless curriculum could provide initial student teachers with an opportunity to know a learner outside their borders and place of comfort. More so, borderless curriculum has potentials for “an examination of boundaries of ethnicity, race, culture, and power and urges us to move across psychological, social, and conceptual barriers to better understand our own lives and experiences and those of ‘others’” (Reyes & Garza, 2005, p. 154).

It allows dismantling of traditional hierarchies in education: A borderless curriculum in post-human thinking could enable countries to dismantle traditional or compartmentalized approaches to education (Smith, 2013). For example, the USA is compelled to appreciate that educating a child does not rest merely on average test scores, but on the gamut of emotional, cultural, and life experiences that help a person’s self-actualizing flow (Kazanjian, 2016). In addition, as proposed by Giroux (2005) borderless curriculum allows initial teacher-students to understand otherness in its own terms and to craft other borderlands in which diverse cultural resources allow for the fashioning of new identities within existing configurations of power. Furthermore, we see a borderless curriculum offering political, social and pedagogical functions for reorienting the historicity and ideology of dominant institutions with the people, cultures, and identities that have been excluded (Kazanjian, 2016). This is against the background given by Giroux (2005) that students often reveal the historical and social limitations of institutions in the dominant curriculum, which directs and frames social relations.

It promotes utilization of technology in accordance with post-humanism: As envisaged in this paper, a borderless curriculum can be facilitated by the utilization of technology which lessens the distance between students and teachers in Nigeria and other countries of the world. It is worthy of note that, such technology has been instrumental in meeting, project grant writing, and mapping the way forward to enrich initial teacher education through borderless curriculum that broadens the thinking of this paper and circumvents distance. Technology has addressed many challenges in this project, such as how dual degrees, training and supervision of postgraduates could be handled between two universities. The use of advanced technologies as espoused in post-humanism is critical to fostering continued engagement with colleagues across borders. Thus, technology shrinks the distances between two countries while promoting effective engagement between students in Nigeria and other countries. This lessens the need for (and expense associated with) continual physical exchanges between academic staff and students since most collaboration, teaching and learning can be hosted using online platforms. This will also equip the student teachers to comprehend that the future is technological, and their teaching profession can effectively utilize technology to learn about what happens in other countries in terms of education (Wolhuter & Jacobs, 2021).

It enhances internationalization of higher education: In recent years, universities worldwide have responded to calls for internationalization of education, and this has become one of the key performance areas of academics. Any university seeking relevance in this post-human era should embrace the need to influence their existence beyond borders; borderless curriculum projects allow nations to enhance internationalization and evoke collaborations by harnessing various technological tools and pedagogical skills. In its grandest vision, such curriculum has transformational potential, especially if borderless curriculum becomes a tool to offer solutions to humanitarian crises such as wars, xenophobia, and systematic exclusions of people of colour, among many other variables.

Perceived Challenges Faced By Borderless Curriculum in the Post-Human Era

While there are various opportunities presented by borderless curriculum project to initial teacher education, some challenges need to be navigated and negotiated to champion social change through education. These challenges largely emanate from the context that states and countries have ideologies they preserve through teacher education, which can consequently limit novel strategies that could enhance initial teacher education capacity. This section presents some of the challenges we perceive which require more navigation and negotiations between countries.

Stereotyped educational policies concerning initial teacher education: One of the threats to a borderless curriculum is the nature and design of teacher education in Nigeria, South Africa and other African countries. For example, initial teacher education in teacher training institutions Prior to British rule, the curriculum in the Nigerian educational system was culture oriented and informal (Obomanu, 1999). The curriculum, (or rather curricula as different communities had theirs), though not documented, provided for the objectives of traditional education which include development of character and the latent physical and intellectual skills of the child as well as cultivation of vocational skill, community consciousness, respect for elders and cultural orientation (Fafunwa in Obomanu, 1999). The curriculum of the Nigerian educational system inevitably reflected that of the British following the commencement of colonialism.

In the same vein, Kazanjian (2016) argues that the Nigerian in this hyper-connected world emphasizes standardization and accountability. By doing so, schools driven by national trends and initiatives fail to help students to become global citizens.

Similarly, in South Africa, initial teacher education is governed by the Department of Higher Education within the auspices of Minimum requirement for teacher education (MRTEC) and universities are required to adhere to the standards set by the department. This is partly because most African countries are sensitive to the power play and the historical and continuing asymmetries in power in international research collaboration (Bond, Marín, & Bedenlier, 2021).

The foregoing denotes how nations have been designed for self-preservation through education while at the same time, there is an overwhelming pressure for nations to open up and collaborate with other countries. Despite the pressure, there remains very limited space for innovations that might benefit students and enhance teacher education through a borderless curriculum. Thus, any proposal based on the opportunities provided by the borderless curriculum tends to suffer stillbirth since the curriculum for initial teacher education is externally funded and influenced by stakeholders, some of whom have no clue about the need of internationalizing teacher education. Furthermore, as stipulated by Postiglione (2016), we should not “ignore how international cooperation in higher education is shaped to some extent by socio-historical contexts that include cultural traditions, colonial experiences, and postcolonial transformations, all culminating in a set of new pressures affecting the roles and strategies of higher education systems and institutions”. However, cognizance of the borderless curriculum stresses the need for negotiations between government and universities to address historical factors which can affect attempts to ensure learners benefit from the knowledge of what is taught outside their borders.

Inbound as opposed to reciprocal immigration: Borderless curriculum project is always threatened by a mass movement of people to the United States of America, leaving countries such as Nigeria to face brain drain. This is due to the perceived benefits associated with migrating to the United States. This does not mean United States citizens are not moving into other African countries; rather, that there are higher numbers of migrants inbound to the United States compared to that of African countries. The implication is that United States of America will forever have cultural diversity and enjoy the pluralism brought by immigrants to the American context, although that diversity and pluralism is a highly localized phenomenon in the US. However, the goal of borderless curriculum is to expose various strategies that countries have used to develop their economies, making them attractive to young people from different countries. If countries are willing to share and solve economic challenges together, it will limit economic migration, and this could be possible through education. Reciprocal immigration among participating universities will allow diversity and ensure ‘fair’ to all participating countries (Beaton, Postlethwaite, Ross, Spearritt & Wolf, 1999).

Limited funding to support borderless curriculum: Funding is one of the major constraints to international university projects (Bond, Marín & Bedenlier, 2021), and borderless curriculum project is no exception. Funding is necessary to ensure the project achieves its intended goals of creating comprehensive teacher education that will address the lived realities not only for the student teachers in Nigeria but beyond where this paper will make inroads. Part of the funding includes developing dual degrees, funding students and lecturers exchange programs, curriculum development for modules that cover comparative

education between countries and finally, funding to equip lectures without PhDs. While we note this challenge, we appreciate the role of technology in facilitating conversations that promote the borderless curriculum in initial teacher education.

To navigate this, post humanism thinking, especially the use of technology, has the impetus to mitigate the challenges of resources. We are convinced that a borderless curriculum relating to initial teacher education is inevitable, doable, and desirable to a better, more advanced humanity (Velera, 2014).

CONCLUSION

The paper is part of a long journey to reconfigure initial teacher education in Nigeria and other countries so as to produce teachers who would have knowledge of the other side of their borders and compete globally to address the needs of the modern-day learner. As such, the paper couched in post humanism showed the opportunities for a borderless curriculum. It went further to present threats that could hinder the borderless curriculum approach to initial teacher education between Nigeria and other countries of the world. The paper presented here argues that post-human thinking in the educational setting should propel us towards igniting the need for a borderless curriculum using various technological systems available to narrow the knowledge gap of the (and about) other. This, in turn, could mitigate wars and threats associated with prejudice about what happens and does not happen on the side of the border. We are stronger when we work together, and with all the opportunities out there still to be seized, now is the time for universities to look across borders, cultures and disciplines to create lines of communication and collaboration (Hamdullahpur, 2013).

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